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AGRONOMIC INNOVATIONS FOR ENHANCING FARMERS' INCOME

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Abstract

Income, which refers to regular earnings from work or investments, is pivotal in sustaining livelihoods, especially in the agricultural sector, where farmers encounter numerous challenges. The resilience of farmers in the face of these challenges is evident in India's notable agricultural growth since 1947, recognised by NABARD. However, the volatility of farm incomes has led to waning interest and investment in farming, prompting many to abandon the profession altogether. In response, a concerted effort has been made to enhance farmers' income by 2022-23, as outlined by the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare. This endeavour involves various strategies, including accelerated growth, post-production process interventions, and agricultural marketing improvements. Sustainable crop and soil management practices have emerged as critical factors in achieving a consistent rise in farmers' income, with methods like zero tillage, mulching, and precision-based irrigation demonstrating notable effectiveness. Research findings highlight the economic advantages of such practices, showcasing substantial increases in net income across different crop types. These findings underscore the significance of sustainable management practices in augmenting farmers' income and ensuring the sustainability of agriculture as a viable livelihood.

Keywords: crop management; profit; agrarian economy, income

Introduction

The concept of income, denoting the consistent monetary gains derived from labour or investments, underscores the steadfastness of farmers who have been pivotal in driving

substantial agricultural progress since 1947. However, despite their unwavering commitment, farmers face formidable challenges. Despite possessing valuable land assets, many farmers grapple with impoverished conditions, with an average household income of ₹6,426 and monthly expenditures amounting to ₹6,223, leaving 22.50% below the poverty threshold. This paradox arises from the uncertainties inherent in both production and market dynamics. To ensure the flourishing of agriculture, sustained growth is imperative, contingent upon favourable net returns from the agricultural enterprise, which, in turn, facilitate savings and investments.

Enhancing Farmers Income

The traditional focus of agricultural development in India has primarily centred on increasing output and ensuring food security, often overlooking the critical aspect of augmenting farmers' income. This oversight has resulted in consistently low and unpredictable earnings for farmers, leading to disillusionment among many, particularly the younger generation of farmers, with the agricultural sector. Acknowledging the pivotal role of farmers' income in ensuring agricultural sustainability and rural prosperity, the Prime Minister articulated a vision to boost farmers' earnings during a speech in Bareilly in February 2016. A timeline spanning six years, from 2016-17 to 2022-23, was delineated to implement this new strategy, underscoring the pressing need and significance of prioritising farmers' welfare and income growth in agricultural policies.

Challenges in Agriculture

Farmers encounter numerous obstacles that affect their profitability and sustainability, as highlighted by NABARD in 2019. These challenges encompass a range of issues such as natural calamities like floods, droughts, and hailstorms, delays in crop sowing, high expenses and limited accessibility of hybrid seeds, insufficient availability of short-duration high-yielding varieties, escalating production costs, inadequate storage and processing facilities, market instabilities, excessive reliance on chemical fertilisers and pesticides leading to environmental degradation, below-average crop yields compared to national standards, deficient marketing infrastructure, declining groundwater levels, farmers' lack of knowledge, and mounting concerns regarding ecological contamination and malnutrition. Overcoming these obstacles necessitates implementing comprehensive strategies to bolster the agricultural sector's resilience and promote farmers' welfare.

Pathway to Enhance Farmers' Income

A comprehensive approach, as endorsed by MoA and FW in 2019, is essential for addressing agricultural challenges thoroughly. This involves understanding historical, current, and future agrarian dynamics, accelerating farmers' income growth, improving post-production logistics, tackling sustainability issues, and enhancing productivity through effective input management. Initiatives like the DFI, which originated in 1926 with the Royal Commission of Agriculture, aim to achieve sustainability and profitability in agriculture by reinforcing extension policies and acknowledging agriculture as a business. Despite initial growth trends, declines in agricultural exports since 2014 have impeded sectoral progress, leading to low net income and growth rates from farming activities, particularly impacting rural areas. Strategies such as diversifying crops with high value and **reducing post-harvest losses** are recommended to ensure profitability in farming, with a targeted growth rate of 67 per cent required. Logistics, central to the DFI, are crucial in minimising food losses and waste, facilitating efficient food distribution, and meeting consumer demand. Furthermore, the DFI emphasises maximising income from each crop unit, advocating for equitable agricultural marketing practices, digitising national agrarian markets, and promoting sustainable farming techniques like soil carbon management and conservation agriculture. Enhancing resource efficiency, integrating newer insecticides, reinforcing extension services, and embracing sustainable crop and soil management practices are also pivotal for achieving **consistent income growth** and ensuring agricultural sustainability.

Crop Management Practices for Improving Farmer's Income

Rainwater harvesting structures

The practice of water harvesting entails the collection of runoff for productive use, erosion prevention, and efficient water utilisation. Particularly advantageous in semi-arid and drought-prone regions, it is an effective soil and water conservation method, leading to significant yield improvements and production reliability. A research study conducted in the Koppal and Gulbarga districts of North Karnataka evaluated the impact of rainwater harvesting structures (RWHS), such as farm ponds and recharge pits, on various agricultural parameters. Farmers who invested in RWHS witnessed notable increases in cropped area, cropping intensity, irrigation intensity, and income across different crops. The additional net income generated ranged from 713 to 2,041 rupees per crop, with percentage increases in income ranging from

17.06% to 87.56%, underscoring the substantial benefits of rainwater harvesting for farmers (Badiger et al., 2016).

Precision Mobile Drip Irrigation

A study conducted over a span of two years, from 2015 to 2016, compared the grain yields, crop water utilisation, and water utilisation efficiency of corn under different irrigation methods, namely mobile drip irrigation (MDI), low energy precision application (LEPA), and low elevation spray application (LESA). MDI involves adapting drip lines to mobile sprinkler systems, delivering water directly to the soil surface as the lines traverse the field. Irrigation levels were adjusted based on weekly readings from neutron probes. Grain yield and yield components exhibited similar patterns across all methods in both years. While water utilisation efficiency showed no significant differences between MDI, LEPA, and LESA during the wet 2015 season, MDI demonstrated enhanced water utilisation efficiency during the drier 2016 season. (O'Shaughnessy and Colaizzi, 2017).

Drip Irrigation

Drip irrigation, a type of micro-irrigation, conserves water and nutrients by delivering water slowly and directly to plant roots, thus minimising evaporation. Another approach, Alternate Wetting and Drying (AWD), conserves water in lowland rice cultivation by implementing controlled, intermittent irrigation, reducing water demand and greenhouse gas emissions without compromising yields. Although relatively recent in India, drip irrigation has shown significant water savings and improvements in crop productivity, especially in high-value fruit crops. However, more research is needed on its economic and resource impacts, particularly on crops like okra. A study conducted in a water-scarce district of Tamil Nadu revealed that drip irrigation reduces weed growth, thereby reducing labour requirements and cultivation costs for okra. Overall, drip irrigation holds promise for lowering cultivation costs and enhancing productivity in crops like okra compared to flood irrigation methods.

With labour, water shortages, and concerns about the adverse effects of puddled soil health, farmers are shifting from puddled transplant to alternative rice production systems. A research project conducted from 2013 to 2015 at the Agricultural Engineering College and Research Institute in Kumulur, Trichy District, aimed to improve water management in mechanised dry-seeded rice cultivation during the Samba season. The study found that employing the alternate wetting and drying (AWD) irrigation method, combined with specific

fertilisation (120:50:50 NPK kg ha⁻¹), pretilachlor weed management, and two machine weddings, resulted in the highest establishment percentage, optimal productive tillers, highest grain yield (8.16 t ha⁻¹), net income (74,477 Rs ha⁻¹), benefit-cost ratio (3.80), and the highest water use efficiency (0.58 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹) (Kannan, 2016).

Mobile Application-Based Irrigation Scheduling

The Phule Jal App and Phule Irrigation Scheduler, created by MPKV Rahuri, provide indispensable support to farmers. The application calculates evapotranspiration at designated sites by retrieving up-to-date weather data from service providers. Farmers need to interpret this evapotranspiration data accurately, determining exact water application quantities and timings customised to particular crop varieties, soil conditions, irrigation methods, weather forecasts, and geographical locations.

Mechanisation

Agricultural mechanisation entails the utilisation of diverse power sources and advanced equipment to diminish reliance on human and animal labour, intensify cropping frequency, enhance precision, and optimise the efficient use of crop inputs while reducing losses across various stages of crop production. Its primary objective is to augment overall productivity and output while minimising operational expenses. Mechanisation is pivotal in tasks such as seed sowing, irrigation, and applying chemical inputs. A study conducted at KVK, Tirupati, compared manual transplanting with machine transplanter techniques, revealing that manual methods decreased labour requirements and cultivation expenses. In contrast, a transplanter ensured uniform plant spacing, reducing intra-plant competition and increasing grain yields. Consequently, there was a significant improvement in net returns (Sreenivasulu and Reddy, 2014).

Fertilizer Briquette machine

The Fertilizer Briquette machine operates on the principle of Dry Compression, producing pillow-shaped briquettes composed of a mixture of Urea and DAP. Distinct Horizon's patented DH Vriddhi tool assists farmers in embedding fertilisers deep into the soil through the Urea Deep Placement (UDP) technique, thereby minimising excessive fertiliser usage and enhancing crop productivity (Reddy, 2020).

Crop Establishment Methods

The critical significance of soil in fostering crop establishment and growth is frequently overlooked despite its indispensable role. Issues with soil structure can impede root development, nutrient absorption, and moisture retention, with compaction presenting a particularly insidious challenge for maize cultivation. Robust root systems empower plants to endure environmental stressors, such as extended periods of drought, underscoring the necessity of employing appropriate crop establishment practices. A study examining various rice establishment methods in puddled conditions revealed that the drum seeder technique proved economically viable and more lucrative than alternative approaches (Visalakshi and Sireesha, 2013).

Aerobic Rice Production

Aerobic rice farming involves cultivating specially bred varieties in well-drained, non-puddled soils to achieve yields ranging from 4 to 6 tons per hectare. The preferred establishment method is dry direct seeding, which enables adopting conservation agriculture techniques such as mulching and minimal tillage. Unlike traditional flooded rice cultivation, aerobic rice can be sustained through rainfed conditions or irrigation methods such as flash-flooding, furrow irrigation, or sprinklers. In Punjab, transitioning to direct rice sowing led to a 34% reduction in water usage and associated costs. A comparative study conducted in Karnataka's South Dry Zone found that aerobic farming systems yielded higher gross and net incomes than conventional methods, highlighting the economic viability of aerobic rice cultivation (Sreenivasa et al., 2016).

Cropping / Farming Systems

Utilising a farming systems approach within micro-watershed-based agricultural diversification presents an opportunity to optimise water, nutrients, and energy use while also integrating nutrient management effectively. The primary objective is to enhance farm production and income stability while minimising pollution through waste recycling across different agricultural activities. Multi-enterprise farming systems mitigate risks, generate employment opportunities, and contribute to sustained or increased household income. Customised diversification models are particularly crucial for small and marginal farmers to ensure the sustainability of rural livelihoods. A case in point is a model farming system developed by CRIDA for smallholders on Alfisols, which demonstrated superior economic

efficiency compared to traditional cropping systems, with various enterprises collectively contributing to overall net income (Panwar et al., 2018).

Mulching

Mulching, which involves covering soil to improve plant growth and enhance crop production, also minimises evaporation and inhibits weed growth. Trials conducted in the Dzongu Valley of North Sikkim highlighted the efficacy of *Schima wallichii* leaves as a bio-mulch for ginger farming, resulting in elevated yields and income levels. The utilisation of *Schima wallichii* mulch exhibited superior advantages and cost-effectiveness compared to alternative treatments, primarily attributable to its higher yield outcomes (Kumar et al., 2012).

Foliar Application of Nutrients/Growth Regulators

The application of nutrients and growth regulators via foliar spraying is suggested to improve fertiliser utilisation efficiency by facilitating rapid absorption of nutrients and prompt correction of deficiencies, in contrast to conventional soil treatments. In regions characterised by low pulse crop productivity due to sandy soils with inadequate water and nutrient retention capabilities, a study conducted at the Agricultural Research Station in Tamil Nadu examined the effects of various phosphorus sources (mono- and diammonium phosphate) combined with brassinolide and salicylic acid on the growth and yield of black gram in sandy loam soils. The research revealed that the application of the total recommended dose of NPK fertiliser, supplemented with 2% DAP and TNAU pulse wonder at a rate of 5.0 kg/ha, administered 45 days after sowing, could effectively exploit the genetic potential of black gram, leading to increased productivity and profitability in the Cauvery Delta Zone of Tamil Nadu, India (Marimuthu and Surendran, 2015).

Conclusion

Agricultural methodologies, including rainwater harvesting, precision mobile drip irrigation, and traditional drip irrigation, contribute to farming practices' financial viability and sustainability. Rainwater harvesting enhances crop yields and production reliability in semi-arid regions while conserving water resources. Precision mobile drip irrigation improves water utilisation, particularly in arid conditions, increasing crop output. Drip irrigation conserves water and nutrients, reducing cultivation expenses and enhancing productivity, as observed in crops like okra. Agricultural mechanisation decreases labour and cultivation costs, leading to higher profitability. Furthermore, technologies like fertiliser briquette machines and foliar nutrient

application further enhance crop productivity and profitability. Aerobic rice production, mulching, and diversified farming systems also stabilise farm income and promote sustainability. These strategies facilitate efficient resource management and productivity enhancements, supporting farmers' livelihoods and ensuring the sustainability of agricultural practices (Adarsh and Ameena, 2021).

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